

Elche Synagogue (Spain)

Entered by Emma Lagno, University of Miami, supervised by Robyn Walsh

** Supervised Entry, prepared from a literature review by a student or students under the direction of a Supervisor, typically as a classroom project; edited and vetted by Supervisor.*

Entry tags: Religious Place, Synagogue, Basilica, Religious Group, Jewish Traditions, Christian Traditions, Diaspora Judaism, Early Christianity

A diaspora synagogue converted into a Christian structure in late antiquity.

Date Range: 200 CE - 700 CE

Region: La Alcudia, Spain

Region tags: Spain

The site of Ancient Ilici, in La Alcudia, Spain, adjacent to modern day Elche, Spain.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Walsh, Robyn Faith. 2016. "Reconsidering the Synagogue/Basilica of Elche, Spain." *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 23 (2): 91. doi:10.1628/0944-57016x14781655923274.
- Source 2: Levine, L.I., 2005. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition 2nd ed., Yale University Press.
- Source 3: Albertini, E., 1906. "Fouilles d'Elche", *Bulletin Hispanique* 8, no. 4: 333-362.
- Source 1: Albertini, E., 1907a. "Fouilles d'Elche", *Bulletin Hispanique* 9, no.1: 1-17.
- Source 2: Albertini, E., 1907b. "Fouilles d'Elche", *Bulletin Hispanique* 9, no.1: 109-130.
- Source 3: Ibarra y Ruíz, P., 1905. "El Christianismo en 'Ilici,'" *Revista de la Asociación Arístico-Arqueológica de Barcelona* 4 (1905): 912-7.
- Source 1: Ibarra y Ruíz, P., 1905. "Antigua basilica de Elche," *BRAH* 49 (1906): 119-133.
- Source 2: Noy, D., 1993. *Jewish Inscriptions of Western Europe: Volume 1, Italy (excluding the City of Rome), Spain and Gaul*, Cambridge University Press.
- Source 3: Noy, D., 1997a. "Writing in Tongues: The Use of Greek, Latin and Hebrew in Jewish Inscriptions from Roman Italy," *Journal of Jewish Studies* 48.2: 300-311.
- Source 1: Noy, D., 1997b. "Jewish Inscriptions of Western Europe," in *XI congresso internazionale di epigrafia greca e latina* : Roma, 18-24 settembre 1997, v. 2: 603-612.
- Source 2: Noy, D., 1998. "Where are the Jews of the Diaspora buried?" in *Goodman's Jews in a Graeco-*

Roman World.

– Source 3: Noy, D., 2005. Jewish Inscriptions of Western Europe: Volume 1, Italy (excluding the City of Rome), Spain and Gaul, Cambridge University Press.

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: Landfill

Notes: To the northeast of the structure there is evidence of a possible landfill full of pottery and glass shards.

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Notes: Archaeological evidence suggests that the apse was added to the original structure and there may have been anterooms.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The mosaic is contained only within the rectangular hall, the apse and the rectangular hall are in different strata, and the two structures have different quality of preservation.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Other [specify]: Communal/Individual

– Social

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: The apse was added to the rectangular hall at a later date, the mosaic has been repaired in several places.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Other [specify]: Decay over time

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For religious reasons

– For political reasons

Notes: The function of the original structure as a synagogue was destroyed when it was converted to a (presumably) Catholic church.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Jewish and Catholic God for the synagogue and church stages of the structure respectively.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– I don't know

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1905, 1948

Notes: According to local tradition, the structure was initially discovered by chance in the late 19th century when someone uncovered the mosaic beneath a fig tree. In July-August of 1905, initial excavations were made by archaeologists Pedro Ibarra y Ruiz and Eugene Albertini. Ibarra y Ruiz held a top position at the local museum and Albertini held several professorial appointments abroad during his career. Ibarra y Ruiz was the first archaeologist to begin excavations at the site, and the foundations were reset during this time. Albertini took over excavation of the site after Ibarra y Ruiz fell ill. Albertini's reports are the only account of the original condition of the structure. When Ibarra y Ruiz returned to write his own report, many of the original features of the structure had already been altered, resulting in a number of inconsistencies between the accounts of the two men. The site was covered until WWII, and the next reports we have come from Alejandro Ramos Folqués and German archaeologist Helmut Schlunk. Ramos Folqués had seemingly no academic training but was granted the means to conduct excavations on behalf of the state by the Comisaría General de Excavaciones Arqueológicas under the supervision of Schlunk, who was appointed by the German Reich as a member of the Deutsches Archaologisches Institut. The structure was later reset once again, and the grounds manicured for the purpose of being displayed and publicized as the "oldest Christian basilica on the Iberian peninsula."

Reference: Walsh, Robyn Faith. "Reconsidering the Synagogue/basilica of Elche Spain". *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 23, no. 2 (2016): 91-123. <https://doi.org/10.1628/094457016x14781655923274>.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

Notes: The inscriptions in the mosaic, especially the northern aisle ("vow of the archons and elders") and center aisle ("place of prayer of the people") inscriptions, seem to support this, at least for the synagogue stage of the structure. For more details on the mosaic inscriptions see "Decoration."

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Notes: The structure is situated in the south-eastern section of the ancient Roman colony Ilici (now Elche).

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– I don't know

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Notes: The original mosaic was likely produced by a local school or workshop and is well-executed. Some repairs were executed by a less skilled hand.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Walsh, Robyn Faith. 2016. "Reconsidering the Synagogue/Basilica of Elche, Spain." *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 23 (2): 91. doi:10.1628/094457016x14781655923274.
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- Source 3: Noy, D., 2005. *Jewish Inscriptions of Western Europe: Volume 1, Italy (excluding the City of Rome), Spain and Gaul*, Cambridge University Press.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1905, 1948

Notes: According to local tradition, the structure was initially discovered by chance in the late 19th century when someone uncovered the mosaic beneath a fig tree. In July-August of 1905, initial excavations were made by archaeologists Pedro Ibarra y Ruiz and Eugene Albertini. Ibarra y Ruiz held a top position at the local museum and Albertini held several professorial appointments abroad during his career. Ibarra y Ruiz was the first archaeologist to begin excavations at the site, and the foundations were reset during this time. Albertini took over excavation of the site after Ibarra y Ruiz fell ill. Albertini's reports are the only account of the original condition of the structure. When Ibarra y Ruiz returned to write his own report, many of the original features of the structure had already been altered, resulting in a number of inconsistencies between the accounts of the two men. The site was covered until WWII, and the next reports we have come from Alejandro Ramos Folqués and German archaeologist

Helmut Schlunk. Ramos Folqués had seemingly no academic training but was granted the means to conduct excavations on behalf of the state by the Comisaría General de Excavaciones Arqueológicas under the supervision of Schlunk, who was appointed by the German Reich as a member of the Deutsches Archäologisches Institut. The structure was later reset once again, and the grounds manicured for the purpose of being displayed and publicized as the “oldest Christian basilica on the Iberian peninsula.”

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Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: Landfill

Notes: To the northeast of the structure there is evidence of a possible landfill full of pottery and glass shards.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– I don't know

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Notes: The structure is situated in the south-eastern section of the ancient Roman colony Ilici (now Elche).

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– I don't know

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Notes: Archaeological evidence suggests that the apse was added to the original structure and there may have been anterooms.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

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Notes: The mosaic is contained only within the rectangular hall, the apse and the rectangular hall are in different strata, and the two structures have different quality of preservation.

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↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: Communal/Individual

– Social

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

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↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

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↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

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–For political reasons

Notes: The function of the original structure as a synagogue was destroyed when it was converted to a (presumably) Catholic church.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Jewish and Catholic God for the synagogue and church stages of the structure respectively.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

Notes: The inscriptions in the mosaic, especially the northern aisle ("vow of the archons and elders") and center aisle ("place of prayer of the people") inscriptions, seem to support this, at least for the synagogue stage of the structure. For more details on the mosaic inscriptions see "Decoration."

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Notes: The original mosaic was likely produced by a local school or workshop and is well-executed. Some repairs were executed by a less skilled hand.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some scholars who argue that the structure was always a basilica hold that the ship motif below the southern aisle euploia inscription represents the Church, but this argument is disputed.

Reference: Walsh, Robyn Faith. "Reconsidering the Synagogue/basilica of Elche Spain". *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 23, no. 2 (2016): 91-123. <https://doi.org/10.1628/094457016x14781655923274>.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural being (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some scholars also argue that the maritime scene may have been a representation of afterlife or a scene from the cycle of Jonah symbolizing death and resurrection, the “good voyage” message directed at new Christians following baptism.

Reference: Walsh, Robyn Faith. “Reconsidering the Synagogue/basilica of Elche Spain”. *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 23, no. 2 (2016): 91-123. <https://doi.org/10.1628/094457016x14781655923274>.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: The seven-armed decorative motif in the northeast corner of the mosaic is a possible representation of a menorah. Scholars who argue that the structure was always a Christian Church have argued that Christians could have co-opted the menorah symbol, but this is a minority opinion with little supporting evidence. For more on the menorah as a Jewish symbol see: Hachlili, Rachel. *The Menorah: Evolving into the Most Important Jewish Symbol*. Brill, 2018.

Reference: Walsh, Robyn Faith. “Reconsidering the Synagogue/basilica of Elche Spain”. *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 23, no. 2 (2016): 91-123. <https://doi.org/10.1628/094457016x14781655923274>.

↳ Humans

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although the maritime scene is now almost completely lost, it is likely based on the extant evidence that it once included humans.

Reference: Walsh, Robyn Faith. “Reconsidering the Synagogue/basilica of Elche Spain”. *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 23, no. 2 (2016): 91-123. <https://doi.org/10.1628/094457016x14781655923274>.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some scholars propose that the maritime scene is from Acts of the Apostles or the cycle of Jonah, but this is once again predicated on the assumption that the structure was never a synagogue and lacks solid evidence.

Reference: Walsh, Robyn Faith. “Reconsidering the Synagogue/basilica of Elche Spain”. *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 23, no. 2 (2016): 91-123. <https://doi.org/10.1628/094457016x14781655923274>.

↳ Human narratives

– Field doesn't know

Notes: If the maritime scene represents a journey for the dedicatee of the euploia inscription, “Sy[... the for]tunate”, then it is possible that it depicted a human travel narrative.

Reference: Walsh, Robyn Faith. “Reconsidering the Synagogue/basilica of Elche Spain”. *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 23, no. 2 (2016): 91-123. <https://doi.org/10.1628/094457016x14781655923274>.

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– I don't know

Notes: It appears that the main focus of artistic display was the mosaic on the interior of the synagogue and the possible chancel screen discovered at the site.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

Notes: The figurative scene below the southern aisle euploia inscription, although it is now almost completely lost, is said to have been a depiction of a sea voyage. Although today we can only see lines which may have been sails, we can guess based on inscriptional and comparative evidence that the scene may have once included a ship, people, and fish. The stone screen (possible chancel screen or window) found at the site depicts birds and horses.

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– I don't know

Notes: It is possible that the maritime scene once included humans.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: In the possible chancel screen/window and possibly in the maritime scene at one point.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: Within the foundation of the rectangular hall there is a large polychromatic mosaic featuring a variety of geometric motifs.

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: The mosaic contains rosettes and a small decorative symbol which may be a hederia or an etrog.

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: There are three Greek inscriptions in the mosaic.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Seven-armed Decorative motif

Notes: In the northeast corner of the mosaic, in the repaired "patch" above the Greek inscription is a small seven-armed figure which is a possible representation of a menorah.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief—as opposed to sculpture carved on the round—is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

Notes: Within the foundations of the rectangular hall there is a large, polychromatic mosaic. The mosaic is decorated with a variety of intricate geometrical designs framed and divided by a guilloche braid motif. The main colors of the pavement appear to be white, dark yellow, orange or red, and black or dark blue. The carpet is divided into three main aisles of around the same width: The Northern Aisle: Measures approximately 2.75 meters wide. Features a maze-like pattern of interlocking braids and square and diamond-shaped motifs. In the northeast half of the aisle there is a Greek inscription (0.18 x 2.94 m.) that reads “vow of the archons and elders.” It is a single line of black or dark blue and white lettering framed by a double-lined rectangle. Above the inscription is an area of repair that includes a small seven-armed figure which may be representative of a menorah. The Center Aisle: Measures approximately 2.7 meters wide. Features a series of geometric rosettes surrounded by squares and circles. There is a tabula ansata near the middle of the aisle in which there is a partial Greek inscription that reads “pr[os]euche (place of prayer) of the peop[le...].” (1.03 m. long). The letters face the western entrance and are black on a white background, shadowed with yellow accents. In the right ansa there is a small shape which may be a hederia symbol or an etrog. The Southern Aisle: Measures approximately 2.1 meters wide. Features larger, more complex geometric panels. One of the eastern panels, although significantly damaged, contains a partial Greek euploia (“good voyage”) inscription (0.12 x 1.78 m.) which reads “A good voyage to you, Sy[...], the for]tunate.” The inscription runs east to west in a rectangular frame, with black letters on white background with yellow accents. Also in this aisle is the remains of a figurative scene that is now almost completely lost but is said to have been a maritime scene. Although Ramos Folqués claimed in 1948 that the prow of a ship was still visible, all that remains of the scene today are lines that may have been the sails of a vessel.

Reference: Walsh, Robyn Faith. “Reconsidering the Synagogue/basilica of Elche Spain”. *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 23, no. 2 (2016): 91-123. <https://doi.org/10.1628/094457016x14781655923274>.

Reference: Noy, David. *Jewish Inscriptions of Western Europe: Volume 1, Italy (excluding the City of Rome), Spain and Gaul*, Vol. 1. Cambridge University Press, 2008.

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: The original excavators reported a small figurative scene, supposedly depicting a sea voyage, beneath a euploia (“good voyage”) inscription in the southern aisle of the building.

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– Yes

Notes: The mosaic pavement is decorated with intricate geometrical designs framed and divided by a guilloche braid motif. It is mostly polychromatic, apart from areas of repair constructed with black and white tesserae. The main color palette consists of white, black or dark blue, orange or red, and dark yellow. The mosaic is divided into three main longitudinal aisles of about the same width.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Notes: There are three surviving inscriptions in the mosaic of the synagogue. The inscriptions are in Greek, and contain several errors; either the Greek was copied incorrectly, or it reflects a local, oral inflection. In the northeast half of the northern aisle there is a Greek inscription (0.18 x 2.94 m.) widely accepted to read “vow of the archons and elders.” It is a single line of black or dark blue and white lettering framed by a double-lined rectangle. In the center aisle of the mosaic, inside a tabula ansata, there is a partial Greek inscription (1.03 m. long) facing the western entrance which reads “pr[os]euche (place of prayer) of the peop[le...].” The letters are black on a white background with yellow accents shadowing the letters. In the southern aisle is a fairly well preserved euploia (“good voyage”) inscription running east to west in a rectangular frame (0.12 x 1.78 m.). The letters are black on a white background with yellow accents and read “A good voyage to you, Sy[...], the for]tunate.” It is possible that the “Sy[...].” mentioned was a benefactor of the building about to set out on a sea voyage.

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↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: It is possible that the euploia inscription in the southern aisle of the mosaic declared the departure of a benefactor of the building on a sea voyage. It is also possible that the northern aisle “archons and elders” inscription signified a special place of seating

for important figures in the synagogue.

Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press, 2005.

Reference: Walsh, Robyn Faith. "Reconsidering the Synagogue/basilica of Elche Spain". *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 23, no. 2 (2016): 91-123.
<https://doi.org/10.1628/094457016x14781655923274>.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Notes: Each of the three inscriptions in the mosaic are formal dedications to different individuals or groups (northern aisle- archons and elders, center aisle- the people of Illici, and southern aisle- Sy[...], the for]tunate).

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Miscellaneous finds

Notes: Reported finds on the site include a Corinthian capital, a stone screen depicting birds and horses, a circular basin, the remains of what might have been a table or altar, and an "Arab wall" found on top of the mosaic. None of these objects survive except for fragments of the stone screen.

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: Differences in the foundations of the rectangular hall of the structure and the apse suggest that the apse was constructed at a later time. Scholars in support of this theory point to the fact that the mosaic is complete within the foundation of the rectangular hall and the apse is in a much better state of preservation.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– I don't know

Notes: The addition of the apse to the structure points to a forced conversion of the synagogue to a Catholic church. This is supported by contemporaneous discoveries elsewhere in the diaspora of Spain and in literature such as Severus of Minorca. For more on the diaspora see: Ross Kraemer Shepard. *The Mediterranean Diaspora in Late Antiquity: What Christianity Cost the Jews*. Oxford University Press.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

Notes: Rocks were used in the construction of the walls, which were reset in modernity.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

Notes: Likely used in construction of the walls and the mosaic.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– I don't know

Notes: There were most likely wooden beams, which are no longer extant.

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

Notes: The mosaic was constructed and repaired with polychromatic stone tesserae. There were also Corinthian capitals found at the site that may have been supporting structures for the building, and a stone screen depicting birds and horses that may have been a chancel screen or window.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Plaster, tesserae (walls/mosaic), wood, marble (beams/columns)

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

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↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– I don't know

Notes: The addition of the apse to the structure points to a forced conversion of the synagogue to a Catholic church. This is supported by contemporaneous discoveries elsewhere in the diaspora of Spain and in literature such as Severus of Minorca. For more on the diaspora see: Ross Kraemer Shepard. *The Mediterranean Diaspora in Late Antiquity: What Christianity Cost the Jews*. Oxford University Press.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

Notes: Rocks were used in the construction of the walls, which were reset in modernity.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

Notes: Likely used in construction of the walls and the mosaic.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– I don't know

Notes: There were most likely wooden beams, which are no longer extant.

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

Notes: The mosaic was constructed and repaired with polychromatic stone tesserae. There were also Corinthian capitals found at the site that may have been supporting structures for the building, and a stone screen depicting birds and horses that may have been a chancel screen or window.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Plaster, tesserae (walls/mosaic), wood, marble (beams/columns)

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– I don't know

Notes: It appears that the main focus of artistic display was the mosaic on the interior of the synagogue and the possible chancel screen discovered at the site.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

Notes: The figurative scene below the southern aisle euploia inscription, although it is now almost completely lost, is said to have been a depiction of a sea voyage. Although today we can only see lines which may have been sails, we can guess based on inscriptional and comparative evidence that the scene may have once included a ship, people, and fish. The stone screen (possible chancel screen or window) found at the site depicts birds and horses.

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– I don't know

Notes: It is possible that the maritime scene once included humans.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: In the possible chancel screen/window and possibly in the maritime scene at one point.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: Within the foundation of the rectangular hall there is a large polychromatic mosaic featuring a variety of geometric motifs.

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: The mosaic contains rosettes and a small decorative symbol which may be a hederia or an etrog.

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: There are three Greek inscriptions in the mosaic.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Seven-armed Decorative motif

Notes: In the northeast corner of the mosaic, in the repaired “patch” above the Greek inscription is a small seven-armed figure which is a possible representation of a menorah.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief—as opposed to sculpture carved on the round—is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

Notes: Within the foundations of the rectangular hall there is a large, polychromatic mosaic. The mosaic is decorated with a variety of intricate geometrical designs framed and divided by a guilloche braid motif. The main colors of the pavement appear to be white, dark yellow, orange or red, and black or dark blue. The carpet is divided into three main aisles of around the same width: The Northern Aisle: Measures approximately 2.75 meters wide. Features a maze-like pattern of interlocking braids and square and diamond-shaped motifs. In the northeast half of the aisle there is a Greek inscription (0.18 x 2.94 m.) that reads “vow of the archons and elders.” It is a single line of black or dark blue and white lettering framed by a double-lined rectangle. Above the inscription is an area of repair that includes a small seven-armed figure which may be representative of a menorah. The Center Aisle: Measures approximately 2.7 meters wide. Features a series of geometric rosettes surrounded by squares and circles. There is a tabula ansata near the middle of the aisle in which there is a partial Greek inscription that reads “pr[os]euche (place of prayer) of the peop[le...]” (1.03 m. long). The letters face the western entrance and are black on a white background, shadowed with yellow accents. In the right ansa there is a small shape which may be a hedera symbol or an etrog. The Southern Aisle: Measures approximately 2.1 meters wide. Features larger, more complex geometric panels. One of the eastern panels, although significantly damaged, contains a partial Greek euploia (“good voyage”) inscription (0.12 x 1.78 m.) which reads “A good voyage to you, Sy[...], the for]tunate.” The inscription runs east to west in a rectangular frame, with black letters on white background with yellow accents. Also in this aisle is the remains of a figurative scene that is now almost completely lost but is said to have been a maritime scene. Although Ramos Folqués claimed in 1948 that the prow of a ship was still visible, all that remains of the scene today are lines that may have been the sails of a vessel.

Reference: Walsh, Robyn Faith. “Reconsidering the Synagogue/basilica of Elche Spain”. *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 23, no. 2 (2016): 91-123. <https://doi.org/10.1628/094457016x14781655923274>.

Reference: Noy, David. *Jewish Inscriptions of Western Europe: Volume 1, Italy (excluding the City of Rome), Spain and Gaul*. Vol. 1. Cambridge University Press, 2008.

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: The original excavators reported a small figurative scene, supposedly depicting a sea voyage, beneath a euploia (“good voyage”) inscription in the southern aisle of the building.

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– Yes

Notes: The mosaic pavement is decorated with intricate geometrical designs framed and divided by a guilloche braid motif. It is mostly polychromatic, apart from areas of repair constructed with black and white tesserae. The main color palette consists of white, black or dark blue, orange or red, and dark yellow. The mosaic is divided into three main longitudinal aisles of about the same width.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Notes: There are three surviving inscriptions in the mosaic of the synagogue. The inscriptions are in Greek, and contain several errors; either the Greek was copied incorrectly, or it reflects a local, oral inflection. In the northeast half of the northern aisle there is a Greek inscription (0.18 x 2.94 m.) widely accepted to read “vow of the archons and elders.” It is a single line of black or dark blue and white lettering framed by a double-lined rectangle. In the center aisle of the mosaic, inside a tabula ansata, there is a partial Greek inscription (1.03 m. long) facing the western entrance which reads “pr[os]euche (place of prayer) of the peop[le...].” The letters are black on a white background with yellow accents shadowing the letters. In the southern aisle is a fairly well preserved euploia (“good voyage”) inscription running east to west in a rectangular frame (0.12 x 1.78 m.). The letters are black on a white background with yellow accents and read “A good voyage to you, Sy[...], the for]tunate.” It is possible that the “Sy[...]” mentioned was a benefactor of the building about to set out on a sea voyage.

Reference: Walsh, Robyn Faith. “Reconsidering the Synagogue/basilica of Elche Spain”. *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 23, no. 2 (2016): 91-123. <https://doi.org/10.1628/094457016x14781655923274>.

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: It is possible that the euploia inscription in the southern aisle of the mosaic declared the departure of a benefactor of the building on a sea voyage. It is also possible that the northern aisle “archons and elders” inscription signified a special place of seating for important figures in the synagogue.

Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press, 2005.

Reference: Walsh, Robyn Faith. “Reconsidering the Synagogue/basilica of Elche Spain”. *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 23, no. 2 (2016): 91-123. <https://doi.org/10.1628/094457016x14781655923274>.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Notes: Each of the three inscriptions in the mosaic are formal dedications to different individuals or groups (northern aisle- archons and elders, center aisle- the people of Ilici,

and southern aisle- Sy[... the for]tunate).

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Miscellaneous finds

Notes: Reported finds on the site include a Corinthian capital, a stone screen depicting birds and horses, a circular basin, the remains of what might have been a table or altar, and an "Arab wall" found on top of the mosaic. None of these objects survive except for fragments of the stone screen.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some scholars who argue that the structure was always a basilica hold that the ship motif below the southern aisle euploia inscription represents the Church, but this argument is disputed.

Reference: Walsh, Robyn Faith. "Reconsidering the Synagogue/basilica of Elche Spain". *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 23, no. 2 (2016): 91-123. <https://doi.org/10.1628/094457016x14781655923274>.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural being (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some scholars also argue that the maritime scene may have been a representation of afterlife or a scene from the cycle of Jonah symbolizing death and resurrection, the "good voyage" message directed at new Christians following baptism.

Reference: Walsh, Robyn Faith. "Reconsidering the Synagogue/basilica of Elche Spain". *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 23, no. 2 (2016): 91-123. <https://doi.org/10.1628/094457016x14781655923274>.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: The seven-armed decorative motif in the northeast corner of the mosaic is a possible representation of a menorah. Scholars who argue that the structure was always a Christian Church have argued that Christians could have co-opted the menorah symbol, but this is a minority opinion with little supporting evidence. For more on the menorah as a Jewish symbol see: Hachlili, Rachel. *The Menorah: Evolving into the Most Important Jewish Symbol*. Brill, 2018.

Reference: Walsh, Robyn Faith. "Reconsidering the Synagogue/basilica of Elche Spain". *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 23, no. 2 (2016): 91-123. <https://doi.org/10.1628/094457016x14781655923274>.

↳ Humans

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although the maritime scene is now almost completely lost, it is likely based on the extant evidence that it once included humans.

Reference: Walsh, Robyn Faith. "Reconsidering the Synagogue/basilica of Elche Spain". *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 23, no. 2 (2016): 91-123. <https://doi.org/10.1628/094457016x14781655923274>.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some scholars propose that the maritime scene is from Acts of the Apostles or the cycle of Jonah, but this is once again predicated on the assumption that the structure was never a synagogue and lacks solid evidence.

Reference: Walsh, Robyn Faith. "Reconsidering the Synagogue/basilica of Elche Spain". *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 23, no. 2 (2016): 91-123. <https://doi.org/10.1628/094457016x14781655923274>.

↳ Human narratives

– Field doesn't know

Notes: If the maritime scene represents a journey for the dedicatee of the euploia inscription, "Sy[...], the for]tunate", then it is possible that it depicted a human travel narrative.

Reference: Walsh, Robyn Faith. "Reconsidering the Synagogue/basilica of Elche Spain". *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 23, no. 2 (2016): 91-123. <https://doi.org/10.1628/094457016x14781655923274>.

Beliefs and Practices

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: We can assume that rituals took place according to the norms and practices of a typical

synagogue and basilica at the different stages of the structure. For more on ritual functions of a typical diaspora synagogue see: Lee Levine I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press.

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– I don't know

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: There was a human skull discovered to the south of the structure, but due to the incomplete nature of the archaeological record there has been no analysis of what this find means.

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– I don't know

Notes: Because of the nature of the structure as a religious space, it is likely that supernatural monitoring was present according to the norms associated with the synagogue and basilica stages of the building. For more on diaspora synagogue functions see: Lee Levine I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press.

Is divination present:

– I don't know

Are pilgrimages present:

– I don't know

Notes: For information on Christian pilgrimage see: Falcasantos, Rebecca Stephens. "Wandering Wombs, Inspired Intellectuals: Christian Religious Travel in Late Antiquity." *Journal of Early Christian Studies*, vol. 25, no. 1, 2017, pp. 89-117., doi:10.1353/earl.2017.0003.

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: For more detailed information on specific religious traditions surrounding Diaspora synagogues see: Ross Kraemer Shepard. *The Mediterranean Diaspora in Late Antiquity: What Christianity Cost the Jews*. Oxford University Press. Lee Levine I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press.

Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Although in Judaism it was believed that God cannot be materially represented, anthropomorphic language has often been used in descriptions and depictions of the Deity. When the structure was converted into a church, Jesus Christ would have been understood to be a physical incarnation of God.

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they cthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– I don't know

Notes: Possible for later stages of Christian usage of the structure.

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– I don't know

Notes: Possible for later stages of Christian usage of the structure.

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that kinship is an important part of Jewish understandings of relationship with God. Not exclusive to elites.

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– I don't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: Because of its nature as a holy site, the synagogue would have most likely been considered a place for healing.

Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press, 2005.

Does the supreme high god communicates with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– I don't know

↳ In dreams:
– I don't know

↳ In trance possession:
– I don't know

↳ Through divination practices:
– I don't know

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:
– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– I don't know

Notes: We can assume for the Church stage of the structure that worship of Jesus and saints took place in this space.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– I don't know

Notes: There is evidence that feasting took place at synagogues in Late Antiquity. In the Christian stage of the structure, it is likely that communion and agape meals took place.

Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press, 2005.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: As a synagogue, we can assume that this structure was used as a place for people to communicate with God through prayer and other religious activities, evidenced by the “pr[os]euche (place of prayer) of the peop[le..]” inscription in the center aisle of the mosaic.

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:
– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:
– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– I don't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– I don't know

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– I don't know

Notes: This could have been a ritual function of the space for the Church stage of the structure, and there is some evidence of bodies being placed in synagogues prior to burials.

Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years, Second Edition.* Yale University Press, 2005.

Are festivals present:

– I don't know

Notes: During the time it was a synagogue, it is likely that the structure was the venue for Jewish festivals in the community.

Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years, Second Edition.* Yale University Press, 2005.

Are material offerings present:

– I don't know

Notes: Coins and dove bones discovered in a cavity of the building could be evidence of an offering box.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– I don't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:
– I don't know

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance)
– I don't know

Notes: For information on ritual cleansing cross-culturally see: Patton, Kimberley Christine. *The Sea Can Wash Away All Evils: Modern Marine Pollution and the Ancient Cathartic Ocean*. Columbia University, 2007.

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:
– Yes

Notes: There is evidence that certain sections of the mosaic have undergone repairs.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff
– I don't know

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings are present:

– I don't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings are present:

– I don't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– I don't know

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: There was a human skull discovered to the south of the structure, but due to the incomplete nature of the archaeological record there has been no analysis of what this find means.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– I don't know

Notes: We can assume for the Church stage of the structure that worship of Jesus and saints took place in this space.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– I don't know

Notes: This could have been a ritual function of the space for the Church stage of the structure, and there is some evidence of bodies being placed in synagogues prior to burials.

Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press, 2005.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: For more detailed information on specific religious traditions surrounding Diaspora synagogues see: Ross Kraemer Shepard. *The Mediterranean Diaspora in Late Antiquity: What Christianity Cost the Jews*. Oxford University Press. Lee Levine I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press.

Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Although in Judaism it was believed that God cannot be materially represented, anthropomorphic language has often been used in descriptions and depictions of the Deity. When the structure was converted into a church, Jesus Christ would have been understood to be a physical incarnation of God.

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they cthonoic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– I don't know

Notes: Possible for later stages of Christian usage of the structure.

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– I don't know

Notes: Possible for later stages of Christian usage of the structure.

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that kinship is an important part of Jewish understandings of relationship with God. Not exclusive to elites.

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– I don't know

Does the supreme high god communicates with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– I don't know

↳ In dreams:

– I don't know

In trance possession:

– I don't know

Through divination practices:

– I don't know

Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Only through monarch:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– I don't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings are present:

– I don't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Are mixed human-divine beings are present:

– I don't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– I don't know

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– I don't know

Notes: Because of the nature of the structure as a religious space, it is likely that supernatural monitoring was present according to the norms associated with the synagogue and basilica stages of the building. For more on diaspora synagogue functions see: Lee Levine I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: As a synagogue, we can assume that this structure was used as a place for people to communicate with God through prayer and other religious activities, evidenced by the “pr[os]euche (place of prayer) of the peop[le...]” inscription in the center aisle of the mosaic.

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: We can assume that rituals took place according to the norms and practices of a typical synagogue and basilica at the different stages of the structure. For more on ritual functions of a typical diaspora synagogue see: Lee Levine I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– I don't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– I don't know

Are material offerings present:

– I don't know

Notes: Coins and dove bones discovered in a cavity of the building could be evidence of an offering

box.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– I don't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Is it required:

– I don't know

Is there cleansing (for the maintenance)

– I don't know

Notes: For information on ritual cleansing cross-culturally see: Patton, Kimberley Christine. *The Sea Can Wash Away All Evils: Modern Marine Pollution and the Ancient Cathartic Ocean*. Columbia University, 2007.

Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: There is evidence that certain sections of the mosaic have undergone repairs.

Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff

– I don't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– I don't know

Notes: For information on Christian pilgrimage see: Falcasantos, Rebecca Stephens. "Wandering Wombs, Inspired Intellectuals: Christian Religious Travel in Late Antiquity." *Journal of Early Christian Studies*, vol. 25, no. 1, 2017, pp. 89-117., doi:10.1353/earl.2017.0003.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– I don't know

Notes: There is evidence that feasting took place at synagogues in Late Antiquity. In the Christian stage of the structure, it is likely that communion and agape meals took place.

Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press, 2005.

Are festivals present:

– I don't know

Notes: During the time it was a synagogue, it is likely that the structure was the venue for Jewish festivals in the community.

Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press, 2005.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– I don't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: Because of its nature as a holy site, the synagogue would have most likely been considered a place for healing.

Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press, 2005.

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Notes: The inscriptions in each aisle of the mosaic are evidence of a bureaucracy because they illustrate a hierarchical system of patronage. It is likely that each aisle was contributed by a wealthy individual or group within the community, who would have held positions of power for their contributions to the synagogue. For example, comparative evidence suggests that "Sy[...], the for]tunate" mentioned in the euploia inscription in the southern aisle was a likely benefactor of the synagogue. The dedicatory "archons and elders" inscription in the northern aisle indicates special status for wealthy and well-respected contributors to the synagogue.

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently
– I don't know

↳ Is a bureaucracy present temporarily/seasonally
– I don't know

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– I don't know

Notes: Given the communal services most likely provided while the structure was a synagogue, it is possible that non-religious writing was stored there.

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

Notes: When the structure was a synagogue, it would have been the central communal institution in the Jewish community. It can therefore be assumed that many communal services were provided or took place in the synagogue.

Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press, 2005.

Public food distribution and/or storage

– I don't know

Notes: There is evidence to suggest that meals were often held in synagogues and that food was distributed to those in need.

Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press, 2005.

Place for civic functions (census, elections, others)

– Yes

Notes: Synagogues were often meeting places for professional and social groups, and were the primary spaces for decision-making in Jewish communities.

Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press, 2005.

Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.)

– I don't know

Notes: Synagogues were often venues for Jewish communal court and served as a place for inflicting punishment.

Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press, 2005.

Function for water management

– I don't know

Part of the transportation network

– I don't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Education

Notes: Synagogues often acted as places of study for children and adults.

Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press, 2005.

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintaince of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: According to the extant evidence, this structure appears to have been a synagogue that was later converted into a church with the addition of the apse to the rectangular hall. We can therefore presume that if this structure were a religious space used for religious ritual, there would have been religious specialists in charge of those rituals at the time.

Reference: Walsh, Robyn Faith. "Reconsidering the Synagogue/basilica of Elche Spain". *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 23, no. 2 (2016): 91-123. <https://doi.org/10.1628/094457016x14781655923274>.

↳ Present full time

– I don't know

Notes: Assuming that the structure functioned as a typical synagogue, and later a church, it is likely that someone was present full time.

↳ Present part time

– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender

– I don't know

Notes: We can presume that they were male, given the inscriptional and doctrinal evidence. For more on gender and priesthood see: Kraemer, Ross Shepard. *Her Share of the Blessings: Women's Religions among Pagans, Jews, and Christians in the Greco-Roman World*. Oxford University Press, 1992.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity

– Yes

Notes: When the structure was a synagogue, the religious specialists would have been ethnically Judean. For more on Jewish as an ethnic category see: Hodge, Caroline Johnson. *If Sons, Then Heirs: a Study of Kinship and Ethnicity in the Letters of Paul*. Oxford University Press, 2007.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast

– I don't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life
– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:
– Yes

Notes: As both a synagogue and church, there would have been well-established hierarchies within the religious traditions by the time the structure was built. There is archaeological evidence of hierarchical social organization in the mosaic of the synagogue. The inscription in the northern aisle of the mosaic, "vow of the archons and elders" suggests hierarchical organization. The euploia inscription in the southern aisle points to a hierarchical system of patronage in which "Sy[...], the for]tunate" would have presumably had more social power than a typical lay person. This does not directly indicate a hierarchy of religious specialists, but is significant in understanding the social organization of the community at this time.

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy
– I don't know

Notes: It is possible that the northern aisle inscription would have indicated the existence of special seating reserved for leaders in the community.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:
– I don't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):
– Yes

Notes: It is possible that the synagogue controlled communal funds used for charity purposes and community dues. The euploia inscription demonstrates that those who provided these funds would have received certain privileges and occupied positions of power within the community.

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place
– I don't know

↳ Does this place lease out land
– I don't know

↳ Does this place lease out tools
– I don't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place
– Yes

↳ Are they written

– Yes

Notes: Reading and study of the Torah would have been a central practice in the synagogue.

Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press, 2005.

↳ Are they written at this place

– I don't know

↳ Are they oral

– No

Notes: Oral recitation of the Torah would have been an important practice in the synagogue.

Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press, 2005.

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place

– No

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place

– Yes

Notes: The Torah scrolls stored and used in the synagogue would have been regarded as incredibly sacred.

Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press, 2005.

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration

– I don't know

↳ Housed within the place/structure

– Yes

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s)

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– I don't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– I don't know

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: According to the extant evidence, this structure appears to have been a synagogue that was later converted into a church with the addition of the apse to the rectangular hall. We can therefore presume that if this structure were a religious space used for religious ritual, there would have been religious specialists in charge of those rituals at the time.

Reference: Walsh, Robyn Faith. "Reconsidering the Synagogue/basilica of Elche Spain". *Jewish Studies Quarterly* 23, no. 2 (2016): 91-123. <https://doi.org/10.1628/094457016x14781655923274>.

↳ Present full time

– I don't know

Notes: Assuming that the structure functioned as a typical synagogue, and later a church, it is likely that someone was present full time.

↳ Present part time

– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender

– I don't know

Notes: We can presume that they were male, given the inscriptional and doctrinal evidence. For more on gender and priesthood see: Kraemer, Ross Shepard. *Her Share of the Blessings: Women's Religions among Pagans, Jews, and Christians in the Greco-Roman World*. Oxford University Press, 1992.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity

– Yes

Notes: When the structure was a synagogue, the religious specialists would have been ethnically Judean. For more on Jewish as an ethnic category see: Hodge, Caroline Johnson. If

Sons, Then Heirs: a Study of Kinship and Ethnicity in the Letters of Paul. Oxford University Press, 2007.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast
– I don't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicate to the place for life
– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:
– Yes

Notes: As both a synagogue and church, there would have been well-established hierarchies within the religious traditions by the time the structure was built. There is archaeological evidence of hierarchal social organization in the mosaic of the synagogue. The inscription in the northern aisle of the mosaic, "vow of the archons and elders" suggests hierarchal organization. The euploia inscription in the southern aisle points to a hierarchal system of patronage in which "Sy[...], the for]tunate" would have presumably had more social power than a typical lay person. This does not directly indicate a hierarchy of religious specialists, but is significant in understanding the social organization of the community at this time.

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy
– I don't know

Notes: It is possible that the northern aisle inscription would have indicated the existence of special seating reserved for leaders in the community.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:
– I don't know

Is this palce used for the training of religious specialists:
– I don't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:
institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders
– I don't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Notes: The inscriptions in each aisle of the mosaic are evidence of a bureaucracy because they illustrate a hierarchal system of patronage. It is likely that each aisle was contributed by a wealthy individual or group within the community, who would have held positions of power for their contributions to the synagogue. For example, comparative evidence suggests that "Sy[... the for]tunate" mentioned in the euploia inscription in the southern aisle was a likely benefactor of the synagogue. The dedicatory "archons and elders" inscription in the northern aisle indicates special status for wealthy and well-respected contributors to the synagogue.

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently
– I don't know

↳ Is a bureaucracy present temporarily/seasonally
– I don't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: It is possible that the synagogue controlled communal funds used for charity purposes and community dues. The euploia inscription demonstrates that those who provided these funds would have received certain privileges and occupied positions of power within the community.

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place
– I don't know

↳ Does this place lease out land
– I don't know

↳ Does this place lease out tools
– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

Notes: When the structure was a synagogue, it would have been the central communal institution in the Jewish community. It can therefore be assumed that many communal services were provided or took place in the synagogue.

Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press, 2005.

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage

– I don't know

Notes: There is evidence to suggest that meals were often held in synagogues and that food was distributed to those in need.

Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press, 2005.

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others)

– Yes

Notes: Synagogues were often meeting places for professional and social groups, and were the primary spaces for decision-making in Jewish communities.

Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press, 2005.

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.)

– I don't know

Notes: Synagogues were often venues for Jewish communal court and served as a place for inflicting punishment.

Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press, 2005.

↳ Function for water management

– I don't know

↳ Part of the transportation network

– I don't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Education

Notes: Synagogues often acted as places of study for children and adults.

Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press, 2005.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– I don't know

Notes: Given the communal services most likely provided while the structure was a synagogue, it is possible that non-religious writing was stored there.

Are there scriptures associated with this place

– Yes

↳ Are they written

– Yes

Notes: Reading and study of the Torah would have been a central practice in the synagogue.

Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press, 2005.

↳ Are they written at this place

– I don't know

↳ Are they oral

– No

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↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place

– No

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures

– Yes

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Reference: Levine, Lee I.. *The Ancient Synagogue: The First Thousand Years*, Second Edition. Yale University Press, 2005.

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration

– I don't know

↳ Housed within the place/structure

